

Geodetic Investigation Coal Stockpile Volume Measured from a Mining Site in Okaba, Ankpa L.G.A, Kogi State.

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ABSTRACT

Traditional methods of stockpile data acquisition can only go so far, there is need for geodetic surveyors who need to measure accurately large quantity of coal stockpile to utilize modern measuring methodology that is safer, accurate and minimize time consumption. Again, there have been several debates in okaba site on the computation methods that is suitable for determining accurately the volume of a stockpile, hence comes the aims of the project, to investigate two novel surveying technologies that are safer and most convenient to be used in the coal mining site and different volume computation methods that are efficient and yield the best result, using a stockpile site in Ankpa as case study. The objectives are; to establish GCP points using RTK GNSS, to acquire coal stockpile 3D data using GNSS and UAV Drone, to evaluate the accuracy of volume computation using different software and comparing the results of the two datasets. From the results investigated, the UAV measurement produced a volume of 3060.82 m³, the GNSS RTK measurement produced a volume of 2979.92 m³, the difference in percentage between the two measurement is 2.79% which is within the set legitimate error of $\pm 3\%$. The time spent, costing and risk assessment proves UAV to be better since it's remotely operated and captured much dataset in lesser time. The triangulated method in PIX4D Mapper is suitable for volume computation since the entire boundary of the stockpile is visible and the surface is relatively flat. Surfer, Global Mapper and AutoCAD Civil 3D results has proven to be consistent when creating both base surface and comparison surface to compute volume of a cone shaped stockpile for the two datasets, the result of TIN volume surface has proven to be the best since it yielded the most consistent result in the methods used by different software, specifically for this type of stockpile shape.

Keywords: AutoCAD Civil3D, GCP, Global Mapper, GNSS, PIX4DMapper, RTK, TIN, UAV

1. Introduction

Across the world, it is often a prerequisite for most civil and mining engineering projects and sites that massive amounts of materials are either removed or added to a site as a portion of the stockpile rations (Wang *et al.*, 2017). These processes form a considerable portion of the overall cost to a mission (Chidze, Zhou and Roberts 2016). Therefore, to effectively manage such piles of construction materials whose morphology evolves and changes very quickly, a timely gathering of data is necessary, and this typically requires frequent and repetitive surveys of the area (Long *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, accurate data with a high temporal frequency which results must comply with the needs for engineering geodesy is essential for such a mission (Raeva *et al.*, 2016). UAVs has recently offered the possibility to complete these tasks with accuracy, speed and evidence (Nex and Remondino, 2014). Controversially, the deployment of the UAVs over the African continent within the construction industry is relatively new and yet limited to only a few application operations (Siebert and Teizer, 2014). Key among these operations is progress monitoring and volumetric measurements at construction sites (Howard *et al.*, 2020).

In the current state, most construction projects still rely entirely on the traditional ground-based survey methods to collect data for the estimations of volumes of piles of construction materials (Kelsey, 2017). These include the conventional point wise methods of the total station (TS) and GNSS (global navigation satellite system) measurements which are not sustainable for capacious 3D mapping. Data collection for volume estimation using these ground-based techniques can be hard, tedious and largely inaccurate for large piles (Siriba *et al.*, 2015). Stockpiles are usually uneven, on sloppy ground, and frequently not easy to be fully accessed while taking measurements. Furthermore, these methods are time-consuming and tend to offer limitations in terms of the frequency of data collection thereby increasing the costs of operations.

In comparisons, with the introduction of new remote sensing technologies such as UAVs in the Ugandan surveying and construction industry, it is increasingly becoming more possible that accurate and frequent monitoring and measurements of stockpile volumes from surfaces can be made (Mora *et al.*, 2020). Compared to Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data, UAV solution is low-cost and easy to use, while allowing the production of a Digital Surface Model (DSM) with a similar accuracy (Long *et al.*, 2016). According to a study by Tatum and Liu, 2017b, the choice of data acquisition and computation methods being raster or vector modelling do not only determine the accuracy of the measurements but also can show the time and cost that will be spent in the operation.

UAV becomes great potential to the acquisition of inexpensive aerial imagery of the surfaces that can be used in the estimation of volumes of stockpiles at a fraction of cost and time compared to the methods such as the use of total stations, GNSS techniques and including the conventional photogrammetry and the laser scanning technology (Nex and Remondino, 2014). Adding the adoption of such a technology may minimize the delays and costs overruns in projects (Alinaitwe *et al.*, 2013). In conclusion, this study proposed to fill some gaps that earlier researchers have failed to look at, in previous cases where large volumes of stockpile existed, measurement of stockpile is done using ground survey techniques and high-cost Drones, despite these researches results, companies still find it challenging to discover the shortage in their volumes if it's as a result of data acquisition methodology used or as a result of the computation software. In this case, the data acquisition methods looking at; safety, accuracy, costing and time and volume computation methods using different software and algorithm were investigated, hence this project.

2. Study area

The study area is in a coal Mining Company in okaba, Ankpa local government, Kogi state. Okaba, is about 20km northeast of Ankpa, and serves as the headquarters of Ojoku district in Ankpa Local

3. Materials and methods

For this investigation, two methodologies were used for collecting primary data type on site, the first one with a GNSS RTK, and the second with a MAVIC 2 Pro Drone.

Software used were carefully selected for this study. This was done to detect the nuances between them and also see which gave a more accurate result. A list of Primary software capable of estimating the volume of the stockpile is provided amongst which volume computation written in python will be tested. Software for computing the volume of data is shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Software used for estimating volume of stockpile based on data type.

Primary dataset	Data Processing	Volume Computation		
		UAV Data	PIX 4D Mapper	PIX 4D Mapper
GNSS Data	CSV	AutoCADCivil3D	Surfer 18	Global mapper

The method involves the selection of the steps that leads to an efficient achievement of the research study. Figure 3.1 is a flowchart of the steps that are followed from the time of data acquisition all through to volume measurements and results validation

Figure 3.1: A Flowchart of the Methods

3.1 GNSS RTK Data Acquisition

The data acquisition with the GNSS RTK, Leica GNSS 1200 was used, with the base station setup on an existing control point, the rover was used in establishing visible geo-referenced points (with GNSS) around the stockpile, later, we walk over the stockpile with GNSS receivers to measure the stockpile. The estimated time of measurement was one hour and a half. The number of points altogether is 932. 15 points were taking as the existing Ground level boundary points and 95 points picked as the Coal Boundary base Level; Both points were used as the Base points and used to build the lower surface in Civil 3D, Surfer and Global Mapper. The measurement of the stockpile consists of 822 points. Characteristic break lines were measured to define accurately the real surface of the stockpile.

Figure 3.2: GNSS RTK measurement of coal stockpile Lower and upper surface

3.2 Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Data Acquisition

The second dataset was acquired with the UAV, using a DJI Mavic 2 Pro, the specifications of this UAV are shown in Table 3.2, for the study area, the flight planning and time to be taken was made, the configuration of the flights was done using Drone Deploy software, in this method the geo-referenced points (with GNSS) around the stockpile will serve as ground control points (GCP), in order to georeferenced the orthophotos into the same coordinate system as the GNSS data collected. The component of UAV to use for data acquisition for this research tabulated in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 DJI Mavic 2 Pro specifications

Components	Function
Drone	Capture the images of the site area
Mobile	Connected to the drone as a display view from the drone.
Controller	Navigate manually the flight planning during the drone fly

3.2.1 UAV Flight Planning and Execution

The Drone Deploy mission planning application was used in planning the mission before Deploying the drone to capture high-resolution aerial imagery of the stockpile area. This step involves connecting your drone to your flight planning app which then automatically flies the pre-programmed route with your drone and also automates the drone's camera so that it automatically takes images in the correct locations.

Fig 3.3: Drone Flight Planning and Data capture

3.3 Volume Computation from UAV dataset

The volume computation was carried-out in three different software after processing the collected images in Pix4D Mapper software. The exported X, Y, Z Point Cloud data was used for creating Surface Model

and computing Volumes in the softwares used in this research. The following are the software packages used for the volume computation are; PIX4D Mapper, Golden Surfer and Global Mapper software.

Table 3.3: Volume Computation Report from PIX4DMapper using Triangulated Method

Name	SOFTWARE: PIX4DMAPPER			METHOD: TRIANGULATED			Total Volume Error (m3)
	Terrain 3D Area (m2)	Fill Volume (m3)	Fill Volume Error (m3)	Cut Volume (m3)	Cut Volume Error (m3)	Total Volume (m3)	
Volume 1	1437.81	-0.496445	0.311954	3065.26	16.0455	3064.76	16.3575

Figure 3.4: Volume computation from Pix4D Mapper using Triangulated Method

Table 3.4: Volume Computation Report from Global Mapper Software

FILENAME
C:\Users\techy\Desktop\Coal Stockpile\stockpile\drone_Stockpile\PIX4DCOALSTOCKPILE_DATASET.xyz
Total Volume: 3117.2414 cubic meters
Total Enclosed Area: 0.00126 sq km
Total Length/Perimeter: 131.46 m

Figure 3.5: Volume computation from Global Mapper

3.4 Volume computation from RTK GNSS dataset

The Volumes of the RTK GNSS dataset were computed using Surfer18 and AutoCAD Civil 3D, Global mapper. Simpson Rule, Trapezoidal Rule and Simpson 3/8 rule were the methods of computing in Surfer, while Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN) surfaces generated from the RTK Data in AutoCAD Civil 3D and Global mapper were used to compute Volumes respectively. Both lower surface and upper surface was created to compute the Volumes in Civil3D, Surfer and Global Mapper.

Figure 3.6: Volume computation in Surfer

Figure 3.7: TIN Volume computation in AutoCAD Civil3D

4. Results Discussion

Analysis of Time Spent, Safety and Costing in Data Acquisition

The time spent during the data collection and processing of both GNSS RTK and UAV are analysed and compared in other to make a choice regarding timing. The timing of the activities described,

starting from the phase of the set up to the time of data processing is summarized in Table 4.1 respectively;

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Table 4.1: Analysis of Project Time spent between GNSS and UAV

S/N	Activity/Process	Project Time Spent	
		UAV	GNSS RTK
1	Set Up	5 min	5 min
2	Data Collection	13 min 30 sec	210 min 23 sec
3	Image Processing	92 min 48 sec	22 min 58 sec
	Total	111 min and 18 sec	238 min and 21 sec

From the figure above, it can be observed that, UAV would collect about 10 times when a GNSS is still being used to collect the same data taking in mind the time for equipment setup and inspection. Similarly, a single operator is required for the UAV while a GNSS required at least two surveyors. It can also be noted that for the UAV, bulky time was consumed during image processing, while in the case of GNSS, more time was spent during data collection. In conclusion, it can be stated that a UAV offer a faster workflow for acquiring and processing data taking into account the processing computer speed.

The Drone can be remotely operated at a distance and it requires lesser personnel during data acquisition while the GNSS RTK requires more personnel during Data Acquisition phase and personnel needs to directly contact the stockpile with their Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) being worn during measurement. GNSS RTK is much expensive than the UAV Drone being used, however one as to consider GCP’s for accurate location, though stockpile processing without GCP’s is found reliable for volume calculation, a future recommendation of RTK Drone is necessary to improve the accuracy outcome of Drones. Considering low-cost budget, it’s reliable to use the MAVIC 2 PRO drone.

Analysis of Volume Computation Software results of Both Dataset

The computation methods results were tabulated below. These results were used to determine the volume of the Drone dataset and RTK GNSS dataset based on their precision.

Table 4.2: Analysis of Volume Computation results

Drone Dataset		GNSS RTK Dataset	
COMPUTATION METHODS	Total Volume (m3)	COMPUTATION METHODS	Total Volume (m3)
PIX4DMAPPER	3064.76	AUTOCAD CIVIL 3D	2979.92
SURFER (Mean)	3063.432	SURFER (Mean)	2964.797
Global mapper	3117.241	Global mapper	2991.108

Since the volume report between the PIX4DMapper (Triangulated) and Golden Surfer (Mean) are close the most probable value of the result (3064.096 m3) was selected as the volume of the Drone dataset.

The most probable value of the methods of computation for the GNSS RTK dataset was calculated by finding the mean value (2978.608m3) of the results since the methods have consistent results.

RTK vs Drone Results comparison

Table 4.3: Comparison of Volume between GNSS and UAV

Data Source	Volume m ³	Difference Volume m ³	Percentage	Percentage Difference between GNSS and UAV
Actual	3166.51	0	100.00%	
GNSS	2978.608	-187.902	94.07%	
UAV	3064.096	-102.414	96.77%	2.79%

Figure 4.1: Graph Plot of the Volume result between GNSS RTK vs UAV

From the figure above, it can be observed that, GNSS RTK produced more volume close to the actual volume by 187.902 m³ compared to the UAV that produced less volume to the actual volume by 102.414m³. Presenting these differences in terms of percentages, it can be observed that a GNSS produced a percentage difference compare to UAV by 2.79%. The achieved accuracy was within the set legitimate error of $\pm 3\%$.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The research presented the efficiency and reliability of low-cost Drones when it comes to volumetric measurements and encourages the use of TIN surfaces for computing Stockpile Volumes. It is recommended to use a Gaming Laptops or Workstations in Processing and computing Drone Dataset. Future research work can determine the volumetric computation using Python programming Language

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